

Applying reinforcement learning for random early detection algorithm in adaptive queue management systems

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ABSTRACT

Recently, the use of internet has been increased all around the world, the companies, government departments and the video games and so on. Thus, this increased the traffic used in the networks, which generated congestion issues and sent packet drop in the nodes. To solve this problem, certain algorithms are used. The Active queue management is one of the most important algorithms that helps with this issue. For an effective network management, the RL was used, and it will adapt with the parameters of algorithms. Where the suggested algorithm deep Q-networks (DQN) depends on the reinforcement learning (RL) to reduce the drop and delay. Also, the random early detection (RED) (an active queue management (AQM) algorithm) was adopted based on the NS3 situation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The increased using of internet led to internet congestion. The solution for this problem cannot depend only the congestion control mechanism provided by the source node only. The congestion control that is based on intermediate node includes two parts: managing and scheduling queues [1], [2]. Where the queue scheduling is used for network bandwidth issue while queue managing keeps the stability through choosing to neglect a certain packet based on the route [3], [4]. In tail drop algorithm, the router stores largest possible number of packets, and neglects those who can not be stored if the temporary storage is full [5], [6]. The random early detection (RED) algorithm, which is one of active queue management (AQM) types, the RED monitors the storage queue size and the drop based on statistical probabilities [7]. If the temporary storage was empty, all packets will be received with the possibility of dropping the packet, while if the temporary storage was full, all packets will be dropped [8]. RED is considered fairer than the tail drop, where RED does not object the data traffic that uses small B.W. As more packets are sent as more packets are dropped [9].

Reinforcement learning (RL) it can train how to tuning the inputs to the outputs. The RL requires certain states of environment, then it carries out the possible actions in particular states during the training [10]. RL starts to discover the actions and states inside this environment, then it uses the data it learned and gets the reward and continues learning until the reward [11], [12].

The trade-off between queuing delay and throughput is investigated in this study using an AQM (RED) integrated deep reinforcement learning framework for effective network control [13]. Deep Q-network (DQN) is used to create our application [14]. The key Q-network and the target network, for example, are both equipped with experience replay. It picks a packet drop or non-drop action at the packet departure point based on the current state, which includes dequeue rate, enqueue rate, drop rate, and avg

queue length. Following the selection of an event, a compensation is calculated based on a number of parameters that will be discussed.

Bouacida and Shihada [15] introduced learn queue AQM algorithm in 2018, focused on wireless networking reinforcement learning. Through dynamically modifying a buffer size utilizing Q-learning in a specified period, they change the Q-table and refine the Q-function strategy, however check their method for just two and three scenarios deployed. Bisoy *et al.* [16] in 2017 proposed an AQM scheme focused on a shallow neural network with one secret layer consisting of three neurons to resolve the non-linearity of the networking framework and the queuing latency, but their research did not deal with the trade-off between throughput and delay performance.

Reinforcement learning-queuing delay limitation (RL-QDL) AQM algorithm suggested in 2007 by Vucevic *et al.* [17]. RL agents provide topology details from the bandwidth broker that handles resource management and quality of service (QoS) provisioning based on what QoS requirements are met in egress routers (ERs). This supports class-based queuing (CBQ) by endorsing three separate classes: expedited forwarding (EF), guaranteed forwarding (AF), and best effort (BE) trac to provide end-to-end QoS to customers with specific service types. In 2018 with respect to network scheduling algorithms, Zhou *et al.* [18] suggested automated computation offloading strategy focused on deep reinforcement learning (DRL) by implementing a double DQN on the edge node. Comparing with standard algorithms, their solution implied the optimum tradeoff between task latency and drop. Xu *et al.* [19] applied DRL to network trace engineering in 2018 by implementing actor-critical approach with a replay of prioritized experiences. Authors contrasted their algorithm with the commonly used baseline solutions, such as shortest path (SP), load balance (LB), and network utility maximization (NUM), and checked that their model performs better than specified baseline solutions.

2. METHOD

The reinforced learning is achieved through the random interaction of the agent with the environment in sequential time steps (t=1, 2, 3...). At each time step, the agent tests an action out of set of actions $A_t \in A (s)$ that come from the state $S_t \in S$. After testing the A (t) action is tested, the specialist gets a prize, and another state is assigned $S_{(t+1)}$. Through repeating this method (operation), each notion in the path will be suitable to express Markov decision process (MDP), as following: $(s_1, a_1, r_1), (s_2, a_2, r_2...)$ where S_n the state of network, R_n reward and an action [20]. Q-learning partner: state of agent now, action, and reward.

2.1. Process of select action

As for the territory of RL, we think about four components have been thought about: dequeue rate, enqueue rate, drop rate, and avg_queue_len. At each time step t, state s_t is characterized as $s_t = \{dequeue\ rate, enqueue\ rate, drop\ rate\ and\ avg_queue_len\}$ which is a contribution of multi-facet perceptron (MLP) comprising of three secret layers of 16-32-16 neurons for each layer. For choosing an activity, primary Q-network is utilized and it returns two probabilities as a result (drop/non-drop likelihood). To observe a superior activity on a specific state, use investigate/exploit methodology which implies that the specialist makes a move dependent on its own choice (exploit), or once in a while makes an irregular move consistently dependent on a specific likelihood (investigate). For the investigate/exploit system beginning from a profoundly arbitrary likelihood of activity for the investigate/take advantage of technique. The investigating likelihood is set at 90% dependent on the round of the scene at the primary scene of the organization reenactment, and it lessens to 0 percent through the scene. Figure 1 clarifies the choice interaction for an activity. The agent keeps trying until reaching the best reward [21].

Figure 1. Process of selecting an action

2.2. Reward

In the wake of making a move, the RL specialist sits tight for next state $st+1$ during the stretch T_{int} . The chosen activity is assessed by a prize capacity. The main purpose in planning the prize capacity is to enhance the compromise between lining postponement and drop-rate just as to keep away from limitless parcel drop state or non-drop state [22], [23].

2.3. Training process

The agent will choose randomly in the beginning of the learning using (explore/exploit) feature. At each choice, the Reward ratio will be recorded and measure; and the Q is updated depending on the reward that it achieves as Figure 2 shows. The agent due so will interact with the environment and learn through accumulated rewards.

Figure 2. Q-learning algorithm [24]

The algorithm starts by using the action randomly (explore) and an initial state will be obtained. Then the second round begins, and for each round the reward is registered and the Q is updated through the equation above. Also, the new state is changed to the current state [25].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section validates the validity and performance by NS3 simulation experiment of the designed DQN algorithm, the simulation uses the typical single-bottleneck network topology as shown in Figure 3, the network has n senders ($S1 \sim Sn$), receivers ($d1 \sim dn$), and 1 routers ($n2$). The bandwidth and delay between each sender ($n1$) and ($n2$) is 100 Mbps and 0.1 ms, and the bandwidth and delay between each receiver and ($n2$) is 100 Mbps and 5 ms too. To compare, we analyzed the RED algorithm and DQN algorithm's queue length, throughput, delay and packet loss rate under changing of network link capacity, respectively. The performance of the algorithm, the simulation time is 100 seconds. Table below shows the queue length and standard deviation of the RED algorithm and the DQN algorithm. As can be seen from the table the average queue length of the RED algorithm is larger than that of the DQN algorithm. So the DQN algorithm reduces the drop probability, and reduces the delay.

Figure 3. Simulated network structure

3.1. Experiment 1

For the proposed network's shown in Figure 3 the number of transmission control protocol (TCP) session (N) is 20. With the link capacity 0.5 Mbps, and data rate 1 Mbps. Decreasing the bottleneck link (C) leads to increase probability of dropping packets. It is appears by looking at mean, the standard deviation values, throughput and drop rate of algorithms in Table 1. As shown in Figure 4, notice an increase in your average queue length from DQN, RED Yes, there is a little advantage to the DQN algorithm due to the training process that took place on the algorithm.

Figure 4. Queue length of the RED, DQN algorithms

Table 1. The parameters of RED and DQN algorithms in experment 1

Scenario	Mean (packet)	Standard deviation (packet)
RED	115.747	44.37
DQN	114.323	41.78
scenario	Mean (packet)	Standard deviation (packet)

Discuss: decrease the link capacity (C) leads to increase the round-trip time (RTT), and increase probability of dropping packets. That is appeared by looking at the standard deviation values of algorithms in Table 1. We can see that the DQN algorithm outperforms the RED technique in terms of total network performance.

3.2. Experiment 2

For the proposed network's shown in figure 3 the number of TCP session (N) is 20. With the link capacity 1Mbps, and data rate 1 Mbps. The bottleneck was changed from 0.5 Mbps to 1 Mbps. This increase resulted in less crowding and less fall compared to experiment 1. It also shows the preference of the DQN algorithm over the RED algorithm in terms of drop show in Figure 5, notice a better deference of 1.1% by 19.4% drop rate for the DQN algorithm and 20.3% drop rate for the RED algorithm can see in Table 2, as well as a better throughput of 0.1 Mbps, and this is due to the reason for training the algorithm and adapting it to the network congestions

Table 2. The parameters of RED and DQN algorithms in experiment 2

Scenario	Mean (packet)	Standard deviation (packet)
RED	119.959	29.308
DQN	117.727	26.355

Figure 5. Queue length of the RED, DQN algorithms

Discuss: when the link capacity (C) is reduced, the round-trip time (RTT) increases, as does the likelihood of packets being dropped. Looking at the standard deviation values of algorithms in table 2 reveals this. We can observe that the DQN algorithm produces a superior overall network performance than the RED approach.

3.3. Experiment 3

For the proposed network's shown in Figure 3, the number of TCP session (N) is 20. With the link capacity 5 Mbps, and data rate 1 Mbps. In Table 3, values of mean and standard deviation of the queue length with the increase in the size of the bottleneck, notice an excellent advantage in terms of network state, as in the Figure 6 notice the lowest drop rate, a good throughput, the average queue length, and a preference for the DQN algorithm where it obtained a drop rate of 1.2% less and a difference in the throughput of 0.04 Mbps due to the good training of the algorithm can show in Table 3. Through experiments 2 and 1 note that the larger the bottleneck size, the lower the drop ratio, and the less congestions.

Figure 6. Queue length of the RED, DQN algorithms

Table 3. The parameters of RED and DQN algorithms in experiment 7

Scenario	Mean (packet)	Standard deviation (packet)
RED	69.07	9.47
DQN	67.93	6.78
senario	Mean (packet)	Standard deviation (packet)

Discuss: we can see how the DQN method outperforms other algorithms in terms of keeping the queue length close to the target value with little oscillation. When looking at the value of standard deviation in table, it is apparent that this is the case. In all prior trials, the overshoot of the DQN response has never surpassed 160 packets; in contrast, the RED algorithm's overshoot has never exceeded 160 packets.

3.4. Compares between RED and DQN with multiple parametes

To study the effect of bottleneck link disturbance on the network, the following experiments have been executed, show in Table 4 for the proposed networks shown in Figure 3 the number of TCP session (N) is 20. With the different of bottleneck link, and data rate 1 Mbps. Values of mean of the queue length for AQM, throughput and drop rate, as shown in Table 4 show in Figures 7, 8, and 9. We can see the DQN algorithm overall network performance is better than that produced by the RED algorithm

Table 4. Average of mean, throughput amd drop rate in different (c)

C	Mean packets RED	Mean packets DQN	Throughput RED	Throughput DQN	Drop RED	Drop DQN
0.5	115.747	114.323	0.3796	0.3967	24.30%	22.90%
1	119.959	117.727	0.8907	0.918	20.30%	19.40%
5	69.07	67.93	4.935	4.972	15.40%	14.60%

Figure 7. Compare between mean packets in RED and DQN

Figure 8. Compare between throughputs in RED and DQN

Figure 9. Compare between drops in RED and DQN

4. CONCLUSION

Python was used to implement Q-learning algorithm to choose the highest parameter to reduce the packets, where an environment that has learned through network management was obtained, and this will allocate the highest probability to drop the packets which in turn will provide a better network efficiency with reducing or preventing the congestion. However, the generated results were better than those of RED. In the future work, the action choice should be improved using fuzzy-Q.

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